

THE MAIN TASKS OF THE YOUTH LEADER SERVING IN THE MAHALLA

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Abstract: The significance of this article lies in highlighting the current problems and shortcomings in identifying talented youth and organizing meaningful leisure activities for young people, based on the tasks of youth leaders as defined by laws and regulations.

Keywords: offenses, "Youth Employment Program," youth in the "at-risk" category, "Children of Ibrat"

Young people constitute 62.8% of the total population of the Republic of Uzbekistan. Youth is the country's greatest wealth. Currently, various types of offenses are being committed by young people who have fallen under the influence of harmful ideas, become addicted to online gambling, or spend their time unproductively. Therefore, the most important issue is organizing meaningful leisure activities for our youth, studying and resolving their problems. In order to prevent offenses among young people, the Head of State has adopted relevant decisions to introduce new management mechanisms for working with youth, create a vertical system for working with them, address youth problems directly in mahallas, and further improve the effectiveness of spiritual, educational, and upbringing work in educational institutions. As a result, the position of youth leader has been introduced in every mahalla.

In accordance with Appendix 3 to the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-209 dated December 21, 2023, "On measures aimed at fundamentally enhancing the role of the mahalla institution in society and ensuring its function as the first point of contact in addressing public concerns," the following tasks were assigned to the youth leader:

- To meaningfully organize leisure time for young people in mahallas, identify and guide youth interested in walking, running, mini-football, badminton, streetball, and "Workout" sports, as well as music and science. Assist in the employment of unemployed youth and school graduates by implementing the "Youth Employment Program" in the mahalla and compiling a list of unemployed youth and school graduates in collaboration with the assistant to the governor to ensure their employment.
- Meet with graduating high school students once a month to assist them in choosing a higher education institution and specialty, as well as to help them prepare for entrance exams.
- Assist vulnerable young people who need state support in finding their place in life.
- Visit the residences and workplaces of vulnerable youth in the mahalla at least once a month, together with assigned leaders, to help them find their place in life.
- Work systematically with youth prone to committing offenses, as well as collaborate with the prevention inspector to work with minors at risk of committing offenses.
- Work individually with youth and minors prone to committing offenses.

- Address the issues of young people included in the "Youth Notebook," including the effective use of 30 types of assistance provided to youth. Visit the homes of assisted youth once a quarter to support the implementation of their projects.
- Work with and support young compatriots abroad, study their activities through monthly communication, and take necessary measures with the "mahalla seven" to facilitate their return to their homeland.
- Identify at least one talented youth each month, work with them individually to develop their talent, and take measures to support them through available assistance programs.
- Widely promote reading among young people by organizing reading events with the involvement of spiritual and cultural figures, writers, and poets at least once a quarter. The youth leader should set a personal example by reading at least one book each month.
- For the purpose of personal development, including within the framework of the "Ibrat farzandlari" project, it is necessary to constantly encourage the youth of the mahalla to learn at least one foreign language, serve as an example for young people, instill national and cultural traditions in the minds of young people, support talented youth, develop collective and individual entrepreneurial activity of young people and provide young people with employment, education and vocational education, inform about the possibilities of realizing their interests, organize meaningful leisure time of young people in the mahalla due to their limited physical abilities,

References:

- Strategy of Actions on Five Priority Directions of Development of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2017-2021
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PP-92 of January 19, 2022, "On Measures to Fundamentally Improve the System of Work with Youth in Mahallas."
- Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. UP-209 of December 21, 2023, "On Measures to Fundamentally Enhance the Role of the Mahalla Institution in Society and Ensure Its Work as a Primary Staff in Solving Population Problems."

